

SIGNIFICANCE OF TOURISM AND EFFECTS IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11515474>

Abstract. In this article, the importance and substance of the influence of tourism on the state education system, which is considered a part of developing Uzbekistan and serves for its position is revealed. Tourism has exerted outcome of the quality and system of education in Uzbekistan in such a way that the result of this can be seen in the number of young and adult students who set off the country in search of knowledge and advance to the territory of Uzbekistan for this purpose. In order to reach a higher level, the country is working hard on itself, various methods and techniques are being considered. The educational program is further enriched by choosing the one suitable for all apprentices.

Keywords: *Tourism, educational tourism, educational system of Uzbekistan, foreign students, "Push" model, "Pull" model, university, institutions.*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada rivojlanayotgan O'zbekistonning bir bo'lagi hisoblangan va o'z mavqeiga xizmat qiladigan turizmning davlat ta'lim tizimiga ta'sirining ahamiyati va mohiyati ochib berilgan. Turizm O'zbekistonda ta'lim sifati va tizimi natijalarini shunday ko'rsatdiki, buning natijasini ilm izlab o'z yurtini tark etayotgan o'zbek yosh-u kattalari va ayni shu maqsadda O'zbekiston hududiga qadam qo'yayotgan xalqaro talabalar sonining misolida ko'rishimiz mumkin. Yuksak bosqichga chiqish uchun mamlakat o'z ustida qattiq ishlamoqda, turli usul va uslublar ko'rib chiqilmoqda. Ta'lim dasturi barcha bilim oluvchilar uchun muvofiq yo'lini tanlash orqali yanada boyitiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Turizm, ta'lim turizmi, O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi, chet ellik talabalar, "Push" modeli, "Pull" modeli, universitet, muassasalar.*

Аннотация. В данной статье раскрывается значение и содержание влияния туризма на государственную систему образования, которая считается частью развивающегося Узбекистана и служит его позиции. Туризм оказал влияние на качество и систему образования в Узбекистане таким образом, что результат этого можно увидеть в количестве молодых и взрослых студентов, отправляющихся в страну в поисках знаний и направляющихся на территорию Узбекистана для этой цели. Чтобы выйти

на более высокий уровень, страна усердно работает над собой, рассматриваются различные методы и приемы. Образовательная программа дополнительно обогащается за счет выбора той, которая подходит всем ученикам.

Ключевые слова: Туризм, образовательный туризм, образовательная система Узбекистана, иностранные студенты, модель «Push», модель «Pull», университет, институты.

Introduction. Tourism is seen as a gathering of nations for these various purposes. One of the several goals is the field of education. The combination of tourism and education is so important that its role is facing great criticism in today's modern world. Uzbekistan, having a rich cultural and historical perspective, like several leading countries, pays considerable attention to the sphere of tourism. The reason for this is that tourism not only has a socio-economic and socio-cultural impact but also makes its presence felt in the educational atmosphere. It is not mistaken to call it the demand of the time and the people with clear facts.

The mass tourism industry has various directions, one of which is educational tourism, which is currently growing speedily in every country of the world. Educational tourism or ecotourism is a type of travel that combines education and tourism. Edutourism is an activity executed by tourists who are part of an educational trip with a higher or lower level of aim. [1] Although this term is unidentified to a great number of individuals, it is a term that came into sight and developed several centuries ago. Edutourism commenced to become popular mainly among young aristocrats in England in the 17th century, and this process continued throughout the 18th and 19th centuries and has spread all through the world to this day. However, many scholars hesitate to give a precise definition of this term. The abstraction of ecotourism is acquired from the Latin word *ēducātiōn*, which means "education" in English, and the Greek word "tómos" meaning a circle, and the suffix -ism, which means action, is used with a noun in Greek, therefore, editor-ism is the act of traveling for learning or erudition. [2] It is certainly logical to associate education with tourism. Because the main reason for going from one place to another is to learn and increase knowledge. A person at least has information about the location, climate, culture, people, and national cuisine of the place he visited. All learned facts are education. In addition, many examples can be given: going to a foreign country as a university student, business cooperation, tours, educational exchange programs, etc. As for Uzbekistan, it fascinates the attention of millions of tourists

every year due to its historical and cultural attractions. The highest result was achieved in 2019 with 6.7 million tourists, according to the latest reports, 6.6 million foreigners recognized Uzbekistan as a place of interest in 2023. These numbers were not made in vain, the more people from abroad come to the country, the more it will benefit. It can be proved by the benefit of education: it is admitted that after arriving in Uzbekistan, tourists spend their days among the people, sometimes in the crowded streets, sometimes in the quiet nature. Young people and adults are all affected by them. After all, residents are interested in a representative of a nation unknown to them, they want to know more about them. After the familiarization process, the interest of the local population who meet the tourists in their own country will increase in overseas states. Another advantage of going to a foreign country, other than going on a trip, is to study in educational institutions in that country. Along with the education process, the tourism process is also continued. This will help the youth, who are the future of Uzbekistan, to develop their worldview, become thoughtful, and advance their ability to solve problems in a short period. This will create new methods in the country and lead to the growth of new thinking personnel. As a result, according to the latest research, 138,900 thousand students in Uzbekistan decided to continue their higher education in foreign universities in 2022.

The power of tourism has proliferated all over Uzbekistan to such an extent that the proof of this can be felt through the speech of the Rector of the International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage “Silk Road” Aziz Abdukhakimov at the global forum of the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) General Assembly in Samarkand: “Education in the field of tourism in Uzbekistan is developing rapidly. Within the last three years, the number of specialist higher education institutions has increased from 16 to 30, and the number of students has increased from 4,100 to 11,500. The number of researchers and academic staff has also increased dynamically”. [3] The opening of more than 10 universities and institutes in 3 years and the increase of confidence of more than 7000 students in these places is definitely a substantial result. From these indicators, it is clear that Uzbekistan is achieving great results with the help of tourism and paying significant attention to higher education, which is of prominent importance in the development of tourism through its benefits. Inspired by such changes and improvements, young people are eager to become masters of this field. Personnel with strong knowledge, it can be said with confidence that they will introduce Uzbekistan to the whole world through tourism. It is quite apparent from the above points that everything is closely

related: if tourism improves, the state will benefit, if the state benefits, attention to young personnel will increase, if attention appears, tourism will flourish.

During the time discussing educational tourism, the main aspect of tourism is the study of students in a foreign country. Mazzarol, Kemp, and Savery (1997) discovered six factors that can influence student selection of a host country. [4] First of all, when choosing a host country, a student should have complete information about it. Part of this is the fact that the reputation and quality of the destination are similar to that of his country and that his qualification is recognized in his own country. Second, the degree of referrals or personal recommendations a school receives from parents, relatives, friends, and other “gatekeepers” before a final decision is made. This is especially helpful if the visitor has a relative who has lived in a foreign country. The third factor is money. It includes living expenses, fees, travel expenses, and other social costs such as crime, insecurity, and racial discrimination. The fourth factor is related to the environment, which aims to study the “climate” in the country, as well as the perception of its physical climate and lifestyle. The fifth is a geographical and time issue. The geographical proximity of the student’s home country and the time distance are important. The last factor is social connections, which depend on whether the student has family and close friends living in the country of destination. This factor is very important. Because a person will inevitably face many difficulties alone in an unfamiliar land.

Through the above statistics, it is possible to determine what are the requirements of people who are hopeful to study abroad. This will assist not only the countries of the whole world but also Uzbekistan’s higher education institutions to eliminate shortcomings and increase facilities. In his research, McMahon studied international student flows in 18 developing countries between the 1960s and 1970s, using both push and pull models. [5] The “Push” migratory model proved that the flow of students depends on the country’s economic wealth, its economic and educational position in the world, and the fact that it has sufficient conditions for education. The “Pull” penetrating model proved that the focus of the flow is on the host country’s political situation, cultural relations, and how the host country accepts international students, supporting them with a good amount of scholarships and social amenities, in addition to the economic side. It is identified by a large number of nations that now Uzbekistan is among the developing countries. Therefore, it is necessary to concentrate on “push” and “pull” in the education system within the state. Through the “Push” program, citizens of Uzbekistan can be supported to

improve their knowledge and skills abroad. Together with this, it is possible to ensure that Uzbek culture reaches and spreads to every corner of the world. The “Pull” program aids in attracting a group of international students to Uzbekistan. Interested tourists, after coming to this country and exploring it in every way, will certainly show interest in the education system. If the local teaching methodology offers educational programs perfectly to foreigners and they accept these choices, it will stimulate the development of both tourism and education in the state.

Conclusion. In conclusion, in each single area, there is a noteworthy role of tourism in the economy, society, and, most importantly, education which is progressing more briskly than other industries. Thanks to the growth of this industry, culture and enlightenment, manners, hospitality and kindness, thirst for knowledge are emerging and spreading among the people. It should be considered as one of the highest goals to bring the tourism sector, which educates humanity in all aspects, to the highest level in Uzbekistan.

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